

pyteeatea - A Python-based Techno-Economic Assessment Tool

pyteeatea is a Python library for performing techno-economic analyses (TEA) of chemical processes based on the methodologies described by Peters, Timmerhaus, and West. The tool provides a flexible and transparent framework for estimating CAPEX, OPEX, and the resulting net production costs of a defined product and process configuration.

The library operates using two main configuration files that define the settings and boundary conditions of the TEA. It supports various data sources, including Aspen Plus® simulations (accessed via `aspenparserDLR`) as well as JSON, YAML, or CSV data. By linking process units to cost information –such as equipment and raw materials– from the complementary `pyteeadb` database (or custom user data), `pyteeatea` provides a consistent, automated workflow for cost estimation and economic evaluation of chemical processes.

The library is designed as the core analysis layer within a modular toolbox ecosystem. It integrates process simulation data, validated economic databases, and robust unit handling to enable reproducible, data-driven, and configurable techno-economic evaluations.

Key Features

- Standards-based TEA methodology following Peters, Timmerhaus, and West
- CAPEX and OPEX estimation with automated aggregation to net production costs
- Configurable analysis setup using structured configuration files for settings and system boundaries
- Multiple data sources for process information:
 - Direct coupling to Aspen Plus® simulations via `aspenparserDLR`
 - Structured JSON, YAML, or CSV input data
- Integrated economic data access through `pyteeadb` (equipment, raw materials, labor, indices, CEPCI, etc.)
- Consistent unit handling and conversion via `pyteeauc`
- Object-oriented and extensible design, enabling customization and integration into larger workflows

Requirements

The tool requires the three in-house repositories `aspenparserDLR`, `pyteeadb`, and `pyteeauc`. Their required version together with additionally required publicly available libraries are listed below.

```

dependencies = [
    "aspenparserDLR @ git+https://.../aspenparserdlr.git@0.2.13",
    "pyteeadb @ git+https://.../pyteeadb.git@0.3.2",
    "pyteeauc @ git+https://.../pyteeauc.git@0.1.2",
    "numpy>=1.24.3",
    "loguru>=0.6.0",
    "pandas>=2.0.1",
    "psutil>=5.9.5",
    "pydantic>=2.6.2",
    "pywin32>=304",
    "pytest>=7.3.1",
    "pytz>=2022.6",
    "PyYAML>=6.0",
    "pyside6>=6.7.0",
    "kaleido>=1.0.0",
    "plotly>=6.2.0"
]
requires-python = ">=3.10"

```

Configure the project

Set the file locations

Create a file containing the following entries and add your created linked equipment / rmu / byproduct files to the according list. Furthermore, add the links to their data sources together with the defined source_id to include it into the TEA.

Overview of file locations for pyteea TechnoEconomicAnalysis

config_version: 0.2.0

linked_equipment_files:

- linked_equipment_objects-ap.yml
- linked_equipment_objects-yml.yml

linked_rmu_files:

- linked_rmu_objects-ap.yml
- linked_rmu_objects-json.yml

linked_byproduct_files:

- linked_byprod_objects-ap.yml

tea_config_file: tea_config.yml

results_path: ..\results

eval_settings:

id_sel: teea_id # teea_id / tepet_id / short_id /
tepet_db_name

```

export_figure: True      # Exporting charts to given results_path/
                        graphs
show_figure: True       # Option to automatically show result charts
npc_threshold:
    0.001               # Threshold for including an individual cost
                        contributor in NPC plot

economic_database:
    standard_db: true   # true/false
    additional_db:     # Additional file to be included into the
                        teea

data_sources:
- source_id: basic_equips
  data_type: aspenplus
  path: ..\bkg_file\example_process.bkg
- source_id: yaml_file_input
  data_type: yaml
  path: ..\input_files\yaml_file_input.yaml
- source_id: json_testing
  data_type: json
  path: ..\input_files\json_file_input.json

```

Set up TEA configuration file

Change values and figures as required for the desired techno-economic analysis.

```

# File containing all the relevant information for performing a techno-
  economic study

```

```

base_year: 2019         # int
currency: EUR           # $ / € / EUR
location: Deutschland   # country, given in German or English
plant_type: greenfield  # Definition if green-/brownfield plant
plant_lifetime: 20      # [PL]
interest_rate: 0.05    # [IR]
working_capital: 0.1    # [WC]
labor_working_hours:    # [OL]
  calculation_mode: 1    # 1: Dependent on product output, plant
                        sections, and plant complexity; 2: Fixed number of hours
fixed_hours:
    0                   # h/a has to be provided if calculation mode 2 is
                        selected
plant_sections: 3       # number of plant processing steps
plant_complexity:
    1                   # 1: Simple / Highly automated, 2: Average, 3: Complex /
                        Batch processing etc.

indirect_cost_factors:
  operating_supervision: 0.15 # [OS] = x * OL
  maintenance_labor: 0.01    # [ML] = x * FCI
  maintenance_materials: 0.01 # [MM] = x * FCI

```

```

operating_supplies: 0.15      # [OS] = x * (ML + MM)
laboratory_charges: 0.2      # [LC] = x * OL
insurances_taxes: 0.02      # [IT] = x * FCI
plant_overhead_costs: 0.6    # [OC] = x * (OL + OS + ML)
administrative_costs: 0.25   # [AC] = x * OC
distribution_selling: 0.19   # [DS] = x * NPC
research_development: 0.02   # [RD] = x * NPC

operation_mode:
  full_load_hours: 8000      # h/a
  partial_loads: false      # true/false (partial loads not implemented
                             yet)

product_stream:
  name: Methane
  source_id: json_testing   # source_id of data source for product stream
  stream_id: prod_stream    # name of the stream in the given source
  functional_unit: kg       # weight / volume / energy unit

cost_precision: 4          # number of digits for internal calculations
                           and standard results

# Lang factor definition
# Presets available for fluid-processing | solid-fluid-processing |
# solid-processing
# if plant_type is defined as 'specific' then lang factors have to be
# provided else it can be left empty.
lang_factor_settings:
  plant_type: fluid-processing # fluid-processing | solid-fluid-
                             processing | solid-processing | specific
  description: Standard fluid processing plant
  reference_id: ref;6$albr_fr#6
  lang_factors:
    installation: 0.47
    instrumentation_control: 0.18
    piping: 0.16
    electrical: 0.10
    buildings: 0.25
    yard_improvements: 0.15
    service_facilities: 0.40
    engineering_supervision: 0.33
    construction: 0.39
    legal_expenses: 0.04
    contractor_fee: 0.05
    contingency: 0.10

```

Additional database

If additional equipment / rmu should be added to the standard tepet database an own database can be included into the calculations by adding a link to the file as 'additional_db'. The additional_db file can contain the following aspects:

```
equipments:  
  - equipments/external equip_db.json  
utilities:  
  - ut_extern.json  
references:  
  - refs_extern.json  
labor_costs:  
  - additional_files/labor_costs_external.csv
```

At the moment the own databases have to be set up on your own. Hence, be sure to use unique ids for your additional equipment and set up references with unique ids to add them in the additional references files.

Exemplary YAML data source

```
blocks:  
  pump1:  
    Flow rate:  
      value: 35.43  
      unit: m3/s  
    Pressure:  
      value: 10  
      unit: bar  
  heatx1:  
    Surface area:  
      value: 34  
      unit: m2  
streams: {}
```

Exemplary JSON data source

```
{  
  "blocks": {  
    "heatx1": {  
      "Surface area": {  
        "unit": "m2",  
        "value": 34  
      }  
    },  
    "pump1": {  
      "Flow rate": {  
        "unit": "m3/s",  
        "value": 354  
      }  
    }  
  }  
}
```

```

        "Pressure": {
            "unit": "bar",
            "value": 10
        }
    },
    "streams": {
        "power_no1": {
            "power": {
                "unit": "kW",
                "value": 14.2344
            }
        },
        "prod_stream": {
            "mass_flow": {
                "unit": "kg/h",
                "value": 2.1546
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Link simulation objects with database objects

Link simulation equipment with database equipment

Link data from an AspenPlus simulation or a yaml/json file with database equipment with the provided GUI or by manually editing a formatted yaml file for subsequent TEA calculations. To include an additional database see the corresponding readme entry.

```

from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea

```

```

additional_db = Path('path/to/additional_db.yaml')
tea.link equipments(additional_db)

```

Link raw materials and utilities with database entries

Link data from an AspenPlus simulation or a yaml/json file with database raw materials & utilities with the provided GUI or by manually editing a formatted yaml file for subsequent TEA calculations. To include an additional database see the corresponding readme entry.

```

from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea

```

```
additional_db = Path('path/to/additional_db.yml')
tea.link_rmus(additional_db)
```

Link byproducts with database entries

Link data from an AspenPlus simulation or a yaml/json file with database byproducts with the provided GUI or by manually editing a formatted yaml file for subsequent TEA calculations. To include an additional database see the corresponding readme entry.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea
```

```
additional_db = Path('path/to/additional_db.yml')
tea.link_byproducts(additional_db)
```

Exemplary link files

```
config_version: 0.3.0
source_id: basic_equips
data_type: aspenplus
links:
  - aspen_id: HOT-OUT
    tepet_id: util;110$maie_si#33
  - aspen_id: WORKSTR
    tepet_id: util;16$maie_si#6
```

Perform Techno-Economic Analysis

Build TechnoEconomicAnalysis object

Requires config file containing the paths to linked equipments, rmus, byproducts, the TEA config file, the results directory, eval_settings, TEA database usage, and finally the information about the data_sources. TechnoEconomicAnalysis with main functionalities calculate_tea(), export_results(), plot_results().

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea
```

```
tea_configfile = Path('path/to/config_file.yaml')
teea_obj = tea.get_tea_object(tea_configfile)
```

Perform techno-economic analysis

Process all data input and calculate all relevant costs

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea
```

```
tea_configfile = Path('path/to/config_file.yaml')
teea_obj = tea.get_tea_object(tea_configfile)
teea_obj.calculate_tea()
```

Export TEA results

Exporting the TEA results to the directory given in the TEA configfile.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea

tea_configfile = Path('path/to/config_file.yaml')
teea_obj = tea.get_tea_object(tea_configfile)
teea_obj.calculate_tea()
teea_obj.export_results(False)
```

Generate TEA plots

Generating TEA plots according to the plot settings and into the results directory given in the TEA configfile.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteeatea import tea

tea_configfile = Path('path/to/config_file.yaml')
teea_obj = tea.get_tea_object(tea_configfile)
teea_obj.calculate_tea()
teea_obj.export_results(False)
teea_obj.plot_results(False)
```

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